

FIGHTING CORRUPTION IS THE ONLY WAY OUT OF BACKWARDNESS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6669454>

Kamolov Shaxzodbek Komil o`g`li

Navoiy regional school of law student

Abstract: *on the historical concept of corruption and measures to combat corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Key words: *ancient Chinese, Action Strategy, anti-corruption Agency*

It is no exaggeration to say that corruption has become the biggest obstacle to any development in the world today. The ancient Chinese empire had very wide borders. This result was achieved by the rulers of the Chinese empire through corruption, that is, by buying the rulers of the neighboring territories for money and annexing them to their country. This structure, which did not exist, quickly disintegrated due to ordinary nomads.

In today's modern world, corruption is defined in Latin as "breaking," "bribery," and it is the illegal use of one's official position for the material and moral gain of officials. Arises as a result of a conflict of illegal interests of several persons.

Conflicts of interest, which are one of the factors hindering development and growth, are not alien to our country, Uzbekistan. It is no secret that corruption is not only rooted in every field, but is ingrained in the blood of our people. But it was done by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. As a result of the Action Strategy for 2017-2021, a ruthless fight against this evil enemy began. In particular, on 03.01.2017, the law on combating corruption was adopted. The law sets systemic goals, such as raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, the formation of an intolerant attitude to corruption in society, the implementation of measures to prevent corruption in all spheres of state and public life, as well as the prevention of corruption. The Ministry of Justice was one of the first to establish in its system, In particular, the procedure for the selection of vacancies in all institutions of the justice system is formed through an online platform without human factors, as well as in the system of education. Institutions test processes in order to ensure transparency and openness, first of all, in order to prevent corruption, the exams will be conducted in the form of online broadcasts on social networks. This agency implements the state policy on combating corruption in

Uzbekistan. The purpose of the adoption of the law on combating corruption and the establishment of the agency is to make our country one of the developed countries, because there are cases of corruption in developed countries. This factor has led to the development of important sectors in developed countries, such as education, economy, health, construction. We can identify the young talents we want.

In addition, the development of measures to address the problems of social protection in the country, first of all, to ensure social and material protection of the population, and secondly, to provide them with adequate age, health, social status, means of subsistence. In today's developed democracies, the state is fully responsible for the social protection of the population. It is no secret that today, wars in different parts of the world, terrorist attacks, environmental crises, famines, food insecurity and the spread of infectious diseases are becoming a priority.

Therefore, the relevant articles of the Constitution include the norms of support for the population in need of social assistance, employment, including protection of people with disabilities at public expense, the obligation of the state to provide them with free training in modern professions, as well as In order to study the views and suggestions of the population on other topical issues, a special platform has been formed in the social network, and sooner or later their call centers are working. The proposals and requirements include amendments to the family institution of the Constitution, as well as the introduction of ecology as a separate institution in the Constitution, reflecting the rights of not only citizens but all individuals in this regard. The number of corruption-related offenses in education, healthcare and construction has significantly decreased in the country due to the work carried out by the Anti-Corruption Agency. In particular, according to statistics, 1,012 corruption-related offenses in the field of education have been prevented.

In conclusion, corruption can be overcome by raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the whole nation, for which the state must pursue an anti-corruption policy.

USED LITERATURES IN ARTICLE:

1. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev "Action Strategy" 2017-2021
2. Anti-corruption Agency "statistics" 2021 year